

Towards Evaluating Capabilities of Vision Language Models in Ophthalmology

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Abstract. Multi-modal language models hold promise for generalist tasks in Ophthalmology, such as interpreting clinical images alongside textual information and enabling interactive querying by potential users (e.g., community Optometrists). However, their deployment requires robust clinical validation and reliable methods for uncertainty estimation. Models’ abilities to confer the degree of confidence with which predictions are made is essential for clinical decision-making, yet principled approaches to uncertainty estimation in multi-modal models remain underdeveloped. In this work, we propose methods to estimate uncertainty reliably and implement a selective prediction pipeline, enabling models to abstain from uncertain outputs. We also aim to present a generalisable clinical validation framework to support the safe, scalable evaluation of Vision Language Models (VLMs) as they evolve.

Keywords: Vision-Language Models · Ophthalmology · Uncertainty estimation.

1 Introduction

Recent advances in multimodal generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) have expanded biomedical applications beyond single modalities to integrated text-image tasks. Emerging capabilities - such as visual question answering and automated radiology reporting - demonstrate strong potential for clinical use, despite current evaluations relying largely on synthetic benchmarks [5]. Although limited, emerging research on the application of Vision-Language Models (VLMs) in Ophthalmology is promising, demonstrating performance comparable to task-specific unimodal models [6]. However, significant challenges remain. Existing models are prone to errors, and automated metrics for factual correctness show weak correlation with expert judgment [7]. Robust, scalable methods for evaluating output certainty are needed, particularly in specialised medical domains.

The integration of various data modalities, such as ophthalmic images and unstructured clinical text, holds potential across many axes. Comprehensive diagnostic and prognostic evaluations require further data integration, annotation,

uncertainty estimation, bias mitigation, and interpretability. We argue that imminently reachable targets include referral classification, point-of-referral image classification, and improvements to automated information extraction from patient records for clinical audits.

Even for these latter tasks, the combination of heterogeneous data sources introduces significant uncertainty due to modality-specific noise, varying levels of data completeness, and potential inconsistencies between visual and textual representations. As learning-based multimodal systems become increasingly embedded in clinical workflows, rigorous processes will be essential to translating AI advancements into safe, effective, and trustworthy healthcare solutions. Quantifiable uncertainty estimation is crucial to ensure the reliability of automated decision-support systems, improving the interpretability, trustworthiness, and clinical applicability of the model. We aim to develop scalable and interpretable uncertainty estimation methods that can generalise across diverse medical datasets, ensuring reliable and unbiased multimodal AI applications in real-world clinical practice. We focus on low-risk, high value applications that can significantly reduce the administrative burden, streamlining the patient pathway in Ophthalmology, the UK’s largest outpatient specialty [3].

2 Use cases

Referral classification Clinical coding of hospital diagnoses and activity for financial reimbursement varies widely within regions. Standardising and comparing clinical coding activity across providers is of strategic importance to the NHS to retain financial control over NHS and independent sector activity. We aim to explore VLM capabilities - with and without uncertainty-guided web search - in extracting key features (diagnosis, complexity level and expected hospital activity) from regional referrals across London Integrated Care Sectors (ICSs) to identify expected clinical codes. This can be used as a benchmark to help audit regional clinical coding trends against expected hospital activity.

Point of referral image classification We aim to assess VLM performance at classifying retinal colour fundus photographs (CFP) and Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) scans into “*emergency*”, “*urgent*”, “*routine*” or “*no referral*”. Future rules-based algorithms combining results from clinical coding and image classification may represent a reliable referral classification strategy.

Text-based information extraction for clinical audit We aim to leverage VLM ability to seamlessly understand and reason over long text medical information (e.g., clinical notes), using the “needle-in-a-haystack” long Electronic Health Record (EHR) understanding [5]. This will help automate case identification for clinical audit using information obtained from patient notes and letters.

3 Datasets

3.1 Datasets for fine-tuning

We propose fine-tuning VLMs on matched datasets comprising referral information, clinical notes, and CFP/OCT images to better align their outputs with domain-specific tasks in Ophthalmology. While general-purpose VLMs demonstrate promising zero-shot capabilities, preliminary assessments suggest that off-the-shelf models may lack the domain sensitivity and task precision required for high-stakes clinical decision-making [5]. Fine-tuning allows us to adapt these models to the nuanced language, visual features, and clinical reasoning common in ophthalmic care, improving their performance on tasks such as referral triage, image interpretation, and clinical information extraction.

3.2 Datasets for clinical validation

Referral classification A corpus of de-identified referral data, taken from Moorfields Single Point of Access Referral Management pathway, covering referrals from North Central and North East London from June 2023.

Medical image classification A corpus of de-identified and labelled retinal CFP and OCT images from different imaging machines from the HDR Insight database [8] from 2012-2024.

Clinical information extraction

1. Open access datasets
 - 480 clinical notes from glaucoma visits [2].
 - AAO IRIS registry of US EHR entries [4] (access request permitting).
 - All of Us – open access genomic and EHR data [1].
2. A corpus of de-identified patient letters extracted from the Moorfields EHR across all sub-specialties from 2012-2024.

A key strength of this work lies in the use of datasets derived from real-world patient encounters, spanning clinical referrals, imaging, and free-text documentation. These datasets reflect the complexity, variability, and imperfections typical of actual clinical practice - unlike synthetic or idealised benchmarks, which may overestimate model performance. We aim to better understand how VLMs perform under realistic conditions, including the presence of noise, incomplete records, and ambiguous cases. This not only enhances the clinical validity of our findings but also supports the development of models that are more robust, generalisable, and ultimately safer for deployment. Subject to governance and ethical approvals, these datasets may also serve as a valuable resource for the wider research community to benchmark future models in Ophthalmology.

4 Technology transfer

Healthcare VLM regulation must strike a delicate balance - enabling their transformative potential while ensuring safety, equity, ethical integrity, and patient privacy. Contemporary multimodal models exhibit wide-ranging capabilities across industries. As such, a one-size-fits-all regulatory framework is ill-suited to meet the domain-specific requirements of clinical applications. A key challenge in VLM regulation is their dynamic behaviour: the same input prompt may yield different outputs when submitted multiple times. This inherent stochasticity departs from the deterministic nature of traditional deep learning models and introduces unique risks for healthcare deployment. It necessitates continuous post-deployment monitoring, adaptive governance, and new performance validation paradigms. We therefore anticipate that regulatory oversight and frameworks will evolve to address the complexities introduced by large-scale generative models. Later stages of this project will thus focus on scoping the emerging healthcare VLM regulatory landscape with the following mixed-methods approach:

1. **Regulatory Landscape Analysis:** Comprehensive review of existing frameworks governing AIaMD, including UK Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA), European Union Medical Device Regulation (EU MDR), and U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) regulations. Emphasis will be placed on the role of model adaptation for downstream tasks in regulatory approval, clinical safety, and explainability requirements.
2. **Case Studies of AIaMD Translation:** Identification and analysis of successful or unsuccessful regulatory approval and clinical deployment of multimodal models - including review of public documentation, key stakeholder interviews (AI developers, regulatory experts, clinicians), and evaluation of how uncertainty estimation methods have influenced decision-making.
3. **Stakeholder Engagement and Expert Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews and surveys will be conducted with AI developers, regulatory professionals, hospital administrators, and clinicians to understand barriers to AI deployment in clinical settings. Key focus areas will include validation methodologies, clinical interpretability, liability concerns, and integration into existing healthcare workflows.
4. **Uncertainty Estimation and Clinical Decision-Making:** Experimental studies will examine how uncertainty estimation techniques affect clinical decision-making in VLM-assisted referral classification, using human-in-the-loop validation to assess their impact on trust, adoption, and risk mitigation among Ophthalmologists.
5. **Commercial and Ethical Considerations:** The study will explore pathways for technology transfer, including intellectual property (IP) considerations, licensing models, and commercialisation strategies. Ethical considerations related to AI decision support, data privacy, and bias mitigation will also be integrated into the analysis.
6. **Development of a Technology Transfer Framework:** Based on the findings, a structured framework will be proposed for translating multi-modal

models from research to clinical practice, with uncertainty estimation as a key component for regulatory compliance and clinical acceptance.

5 Significance of work

Clinical evaluation of VLMs will help assess their suitability for defined ophthalmic use cases and establish best practices for prompting strategies, including open- vs closed-ended and zero- vs few-shot approaches. This process will support the creation of real-world, labelled datasets from ophthalmic referrals, CFPs, OCT scans, and structured data from EHRs, providing a foundation for robust benchmarking. In parallel, we aim to define a set of clinically meaningful, Ophthalmology-specific benchmark tasks to evaluate model performance and guide safe deployment of more advanced VLMs. We also propose a selective prediction framework that enables models to abstain from uncertain predictions - an important safeguard when automating medical tasks.

To support real-world integration, we outline a translational framework that includes human-AI interaction studies, stakeholder engagement, and identification of regulatory gaps. This will inform the design of workflows and interfaces capable of pulling data from EHRs or referral platforms and delivering outputs back into clinical systems in real time. We anticipate that deploying VLMs in low-risk ophthalmic settings will generate valuable insights, enabling broader adoption in more complex clinical environments and at greater scale.

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References

1. All of Us Research Program Investigators: The “all of us” research program. *New England Journal of Medicine* **381**(7), 668–676 (2019)
2. Chen, J.S., et al.: Development of an open-source annotated glaucoma medication dataset from clinical notes in the electronic health record. *Translational Vision Science & Technology* **11**(11), 20–20 (2022)
3. NHS England: Hospital outpatient activity 2021-22 (2022),
4. Parke Ii, D., Lum, F., Rich, W.: The iris[®] registry: purpose and perspectives. german version. *Der Ophthalmologe* **113**, 463–468 (2016)
5. Saab, K., et al.: Capabilities of gemini models in medicine (2024), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.18416>
6. Shi, D., Zhang, W., Yang, J., Huang, S., Chen, X., Yusufu, M., Jin, K., Lin, S., Liu, S., Zhang, Q., He, M.: Eyeclip: A visual-language foundation model for multi-modal ophthalmic image analysis (2024), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.06644>
7. Tanno, R., et al.: Collaboration between clinicians and vision-language models in radiology report generation. *Nature Medicine* **31**(2), 599–608 (2025)
8. The Health Data Research Hub for Eye Health: Insight: The health data research hub for eye health (2025), <https://www.insight.hdrhub.org/>